

integrin subunit α M / macrophage-1 antigen α subunit / complement component 3 receptor 3 subunit / Leukocyte Adhesion Receptor (ITGAM / MAC-1 / CD11B / CR3A / MO1) : Machine learning discoveries of 2nd order synergy in Meningiomas

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Abstract

Background : ITGAM is one protein subunit that forms heterodimeric integrin $\alpha_M\beta_2$ molecule. It mediates inflammation by regulating leukocyte adhesion and migration and has been implicated in several immune processes such as cell-mediated cytotoxicity, phagocytosis, chemotaxis and cellular activation. It has been implicated in promyelocytic leukemia, childhood acute lymphoblastic leukemia, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, systemic lupus erythematosus, human retina, neoplasm-related fever, Th2-biased allergic diseases, HIV-1, uveal melanoma, obesity, hypertension, type 2 diabetes, colorectal cancer metastasis, thyroid cancer, major depressive disorder, cervical lymph node, biliary atresia, lupus nephritis, SARS-CoV-2, knee osteoarthritis, Kawasaki disease, chronic kidney disease and Sjögren's syndrome, to name a few. However, its role in meningiomas has not yet been determined completely. Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 tumors from all 3 World Health Organization (WHO) grades (I through III) using clinical, gene expression, and sequencing data and using unsupervised clustering analysis identified 3 molecular types (A, B, and C) that reliably predicted recurrence. Further, these groups did not directly correlate with the WHO grading system, which classifies more than half of the tumors in the most aggressive molecular type as benign. **Issue** : Increasing evidence point to the fact that meningioma classification and grading, that is based on histopathology does not always accurately predict tumor aggressiveness and recurrence behaviour and knowledge of the underlying biology of the treatment resistant meningiomas and the impact of genetic alterations in these tumors, is lacking. At the current stage more genomic studies are required to unravel the role of other genes and their interactions with other genetic factors. **Resolution** : In a recently

*ML discoveries of ITGAM synergy in Meningiomas

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published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. Adapting this search engine to the Meningioma dataset, i present here 2^{nd} order combinations of ITGAM, some of which have been known to exist via wet lab experiments, but many are yet to be tested. The reveals combinations might help oncologists/biologists test possible hypotheses that might be the causing factors in meningioma. Further, in my limited grasp, if proven true, the combinations revealed by the search engine might pave way for development of gene based therapies aimed at resolving pathological issues related to meningiomas.

Keywords: ITGAM, Meningioma, Sensitivity analysis, Machine learning.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Meningioma

Meningiomas are the most common intracranial primary neoplasm in adults. They arise from the arachnoid cap cells. These arachnoid cap cells are specialized cells that make up the arachnoid mater (one of the three protective memberanes covering the brain and spinal cord). The arachnoid mater is one of the three meninges. The other two that constitute the meninges are dura mater and pia mater.

1.1.1. World Health Organization (WHO) classification

The meningiomas are classified into three grades by WHO under the Central Nervous System tumours, namely, Grade I (benign), Grade II (atypical) and Grade III (anaplastic/malignant), based on histopathology or subtype (Louis et al. [3]). As of 2021, there exists 12 histopathological meningioma subtypes according to a mini-review by Torp et al. [4]. They are meningothelial, fibrous, transitional, psammomatous, angiomatous, microcystic, secretory, lymphoplasmacyte-rich, atypical, chordoid, clear cell and anaplastic (malignant) meningioma.

1.1.2. Historical perspective

Czarnetzki et al. [5] investigated a skull that was excavated at Steinheim/Murr (Baden-Württemberg, Germany) and consisted of a well preserved plagiocephalic cranium, with most of the facial skeleton intact. Their results of stratigraphical dating suggested the fossil specimen of *Homo steinheimensis*, was about 3,65,000 years old. In the fossile, they found that several features of the inner cranial table were consistent with a diagnosis of meningioma.

As documented in Okonkwo and Laws Jr [6], in 1614, Felix Plater, Professor of Medicine, issued a case report from the University of Basel on Caspar Bonecurtius, a noble knight stating -

began to lose his mind gradually over a two year period, to such an extent that finally he was completely stupefied and did nothing rationally. He had no desire for food and ate only when forcibly fed. ... Finally after matters had gone on thus for six months, he died.

Further, the autopsy report of Plater stated the following -

a round fleshy tumor, like an acorn. It was hard and full of holes and was as large as a medium-sized apple. It was covered with its own membrane and was entwined with veins. However, it was free of all connections with the matter of the brain, so much so that when it was removed by hand, it left behind a remarkable cavity.

This was the first case in the history that documented a patient with a lesion that was most compatible with a meningioma.

Next, in a contribution by Italian scientists, Paterniti [7] documents the first contribution of Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri in 1813 in a manuscript *Trattato di Chirurgia Pratica*, which was never published. Its discovery was made accidentally by David Giordano, who referred in detail in an article on surgeon of Pisa in *La chirurgia di Andrea Vacca' Berlinghieri*. *Riv Storia Sci MedNat*. 1927: XVIII (3-4): 75-106. The unpublished manuscript of 488 pages describes that Vacca Berlinhieri proposed and performed a most bold radical operation. After a craniectomy with five or six burr holes on the outskirts of the fungus, the tumor was removed together the dura mater from which it originated, tying the cut vessels.

In 1847, Zanobi Pecchioli, Professor of Clinical Surgery and Operative Medicine at Modena and then at Siena University, published an account of surgeries performed during 16 years, from 1832 to 1847 (16 of the 1524 reported operations involved trephining

Figure 1: A schematic diagram of different pathways in different meningiomas, as provided by Szulzewsky et al. [12] under CC-BY Attribution 4.0 International license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

of the skull). In one of these interventions, he carried out on July 29 1835, in Siena, for the resection of a meningioma, a defined fungus of the duramater. The case was not referred in the literature by Pecchioli but was described by in Pecchioli [8]. Finally, Cushing [9] coined the modern term of "meningioma".

1.1.3. Pathophysiology

Meningiomas arise from arachnoidal cap cells, most of which are near the vicinity of the venous sinuses, and this is the site of greatest prevalence for meningioma formation. The dural venous sinuses (also called dural/cerebral/cranial sinuses) are venous sinuses (channels) found between the periosteal and meningeal layers of dura mater in the brain. They receive blood from the cerebral veins, and cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) from the subarachnoid space via arachnoid granulations. They mainly empty into the internal jugular vein. Cranial venous sinuses communicate with veins outside the skull through emissary veins. These communications help to keep the pressure of blood in the sinuses constant. (contributors [10] and Pamir et al. [11]) A schematic diagram for different pathways in different meningiomas has been provided in figure 1.

1.2. integrin subunit α M (ITGAM)

MO1 and gp160-gp93 are two surface membrane glycoprotein heterodimers present on granulocytes and monocytes derived from humans and guinea pigs, respectively. Pierce

et al. [13] purified both antigens and found that their α subunits had identical N-termini which were significantly homologous to the α subunit of the human adhesion platelet glycoprotein IIb/IIIa.

MO1 is a member of the family of leukocyte cell adhesion molecules (Leu-CAMs) that includes lymphocyte function-associated antigen 1 (LFA-1) and p150,95. Each Leu-CAM is a heterodimer with a distinct α subunit noncovalently associated with a common β subunit, which play important roles in cell-cell and cell-matrix interactions. Arnaout et al. [14] described the isolation and analysis of two partial cDNA clones encoding the α subunit of the Leu-CAM MO1 in humans and guinea pigs.

Corbi et al. [15] described full-length cDNA clones for the α subunit of MAC-1 (CD11B/CD18), which functions both as a receptor for iC3b (CR3) and in several cell-cell and cell-substrate adhesive interactions. They detected MAC-1 α subunit message in blood monocytes and phorbol-12-myristate acetate-induced myeloid cell lines, but not in cells of the T or B lineages, correlating with Mac-1 protein surface expression.

1.3. Roles of ITGAM in different disease

All-trans retinoic acid (ATRA) induces the differentiation of acute **promyelocytic leukemia** (APL) cells into neutrophils. After establishing UF-1 cells from an ATRA-resistant APL patient, which showed the possession of a single amino acid (or nucleotide) substitution, Arg276Trp, in their ATRA receptor, Komura et al. [16] designed several ATRA derivatives having a hydrophobic alkyl ketone moiety instead of the negatively charged carboxylic acid moiety. They observed that it also induced the formation of PML NBs and expression of CD11B antigen marker and p21, transcriptional targets of RAR α .

In **childhood acute lymphoblastic leukemia** (ALL), persistence of leukemic blasts during therapy is of crucial prognostic significance. Rhein et al. [17] addressed molecular and cell biologic features of blasts persisting after 1 week of induction glucocorticoid therapy. They observed that gene expression changes indicated a shift towards mature B cells, inhibition of cell cycling and increased expression of adhesion (CD11B/ITGAM) and cytokine (CD119/IFNGR1) receptors. Their flow cytometric analysis in independent cohorts of patients confirmed both a decreased proliferative activity (n=13) and the upregulation of CD11B and CD119 (n=29) in day 8 blasts.

It is known that the β 2-integrin molecule is up-regulated in circulating neutrophils in **Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease** (COPD) subjects. Yamagata et al. [18] investigated the surface expression of molecules in circulating neutrophils and their possible role in the airflow limitation of COPD. They observed that both CD11B and CXC chemokine receptor 1 (CXCR1) expression were significantly higher in COPD patients than in HSs (mean [± SE] CD11B concentration: HSs, 9.7 ± 1.0; COPD patients, 14.2 ± 1.8 [p < 0.05]; mean CXCR1 concentration: HSs, 9.6 ± 0.5; COPD patients, 11.9 ± 0.4 [p < 0.01]). They concluded that this overexpression of CD11B and CXCR1 in circulating neutrophils might be associated with the development of airflow limitation in COPD patients.

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a clinically heterogeneous autoimmune disease in which the risk of disease is influenced by complex genetic and environmental contributions. Hom et al. [19] found that genetic variation in the region upstream from the transcription initiation site of the gene encoding B lymphoid tyrosine kinase (BLK)

and C8orf13 (chromosome 8p23.1) was associated with disease risk in both the U.S. and Swedish case-control series (rs13277113; odds ratio, 1.39; $P=1 \times 10^{-10}$) and also with altered levels of messenger RNA in B-cell lines. Further, they observed that the variants on chromosome 16p11.22, near the genes encoding integrin α M (ITGAM, or CD11b) and integrin α X (ITGAX), were associated with SLE in the combined sample (rs11574637; odds ratio, 1.33; $P=3 \times 10^{-11}$). Thus they identified and then confirmed through replication two new genetic loci for SLE: a promoter-region allele associated with reduced expression of BLK and increased expression of C8orf13 and variants in the ITGAM-ITGAX region.

Seth et al. [20] investigated complement activation and associated inflammatory mechanisms in normal, aged **human retina**. They assessed the evidence of complement activation and associated mechanisms in normal human retina ($n = 52$) using a panel of antibodies directed against membrane attack complex (C5b-9), microglia (CD11B), amyloid precursor protein (APP), scavenger receptor (CD36), and a phytolectin (RCA-I). They observed that age-dependent expression was evident in C5b-9, APP, CD11B, and RCA-I, but not CD36, immunoreactivity. Further, immunoreactivity for CD11B was robust on the surface of the retinal pigment epithelial cell, in the choriocapillaris, and in BM. Lectin binding of RCA-I was strong throughout the neuroretina. In conclusion, they found that robust immunostaining for APP in older donor eyes suggested that amyloid β peptides might be one of the triggers of complement activation during the normal aging process. Microglial markers CD11B and RCA-I also increased with age, suggesting a concomitant inflammatory response to C5b-9 deposits in the retinal pigment epithelium, BM, and CC.

Kallio et al. [21] evaluated the expression of the peripheral blood phagocyte CD11B/CD18 adhesion molecule complex as a blood marker available for distinguishing infection-related from **neoplasm-related fever**. They found that cancer patients with infection had higher blood neutrophil and monocyte CD11B/CD18 expression levels than patients with neoplastic fever, those with advanced cancer without infection, or healthy controls. Further, high CD11b/CD18 values were measured exclusively in individuals diagnosed with infection.

Eosinophils are important effector cells in allergic diseases. Interleukin-33 (IL-33) is a recently identified cytokine of the IL-1 family, and it reportedly accelerates the production of Th2-associated cytokines and promotes tissue inflammation. Suzukawa et al. [22] investigated the effects of IL-33 on eosinophil activation, assessed in terms of the cells' adhesiveness, expression of CD11b and apoptosis. It was observed that IL-33 at 1-100 ng/ml enhanced the adhesiveness and CD11B expression of eosinophils even more potently than IL-5 and IL-33 maintained the viability of eosinophils. These findings indicated that IL-33 potently induces eosinophil adhesion and CD11B expression and enhanced eosinophil survival. They concluded that the IL-33-ST2 pathway might be an important regulator of eosinophil biology in the pathogenesis of **Th2-biased allergic diseases**.

Urokinase-type plasminogen activator (uPA) signaling via its receptor uPAR inhibits late events in **HIV-1** replication in acutely infected primary monocyte-derived macrophages (MDMs) and promonocytic U937 cells. Alfano et al. [23] showed that U937-derived, chronically infected U1 cells stimulated with phorbol 12-myristate 13-acetate (PMA) expressed integrins, uPA, and soluble uPAR at levels similar to those

of MDMs. Of interest, only PMA and TNF- α , but not other HIV-inductive stimuli, induced surface expression of the alpha(M) chain CD11B in U1 cells constitutively expressing CD18, the $\beta(2)$ chain of the MAC-1 integrin. Like uPA, fibrinogen, a MAC-1 (CD11B/CD18) ligand, and M25, a peptide homologous to a portion of the beta-propeller region of CD11B preventing its association with uPAR, inhibited HIV virion release in PMA-stimulated U1 cells. Thus they concluded that either uPA/uPAR interaction, MAC-1 activation, or prevention of its association with uPAR triggered a signaling pathway leading to the inefficient release of HIV from monocytic cells.

Hernandez et al. [24] explored modifications in signal mechanisms involving CD11B and leukocyte adhesion in patients under haemodialysis (HD). Through their experiments they concluded that leukocyte activation during HD through a cellulose membrane occurred with decrease in CD11B phosphorylation. Activation also induced increase in CD11B expression associated with enhanced leukocyte adhesion to uremic endothelial cells.

McKenna et al. [25] determined whether activated CD11B(+) CD15(+) granulocytes increased in the blood of patients with **uveal melanoma**. They observed that the percentage of CD11b(+) cells in peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) of patients with uveal melanoma increased 1.8-fold in comparison to healthy donors. They concluded that activated CD11b(+) CD15(+) granulocytes expanded in the blood of patients with uveal melanoma and might contribute to immune evasion by ocular tumors by inhibiting T-cell function via decreasing CD3 ζ chain expression.

Obesity is characterized by a state of chronic mild inflammation, with raised circulating levels of inflammatory markers. Sabri et al. [26] evaluated the level of serum mediators concerned in inflammation and monocyte activation (TNF- α , hs-CRP, MCP-1) together with percentage of CD11B expression on monocytes in a group of morbidly obese individuals (n = 20) before and (3-6 months) after restrictive surgery, and in 15 healthy normal weight individuals. They observed that morbidly obese individuals (before surgical weight loss) had significantly increased levels of MCP-1, TNF- α , hs-CRP, CD11B expression on monocytes as compared to controls. Levels of MCP-1, TNF- α , hs-CRP were significantly decreased 3 to 6 months after restrictive surgery than before the operation. Their data suggested that the studied serum and monocyte parameters may link obesity with systemic inflammation and metabolic disorders.

Hypertension, a key risk factor for stroke, cardiovascular disease and dementia. Because blood pressure increases with age, Rea et al. [27] measured baseline and (TNF- α)-stimulated CD11B/CD18 adhesion molecule expression on leucocytes to assess any association between the two. In 38 subjects (mean age 85 years), consecutively enrolled from Belfast Elderly Longitudinal Free-Living Aging Study (BELFAST), they observed that baseline and TNF- α -stimulated CD11B/CD18 expression on separated monocytes and neutrophils increased with systolic blood pressure >120 mmHg and for lymphocytes, with diastolic blood pressure >80 mmHg.

Cardiovascular complications are the leading cause of mortality in **type 2 diabetes** (T2DM), in which onset and progression of atherosclerosis is linked to chronic inflammation. Activation status of innate immune cells (granulocytes [Gc], monocytes [Mc]), as reflected by increased CD11B, CD66b, and other surface markers, increased their endothelial and cytokines/chemokines release. Horvath et al. [28] found that hyperglycemic patients with T2DM had significantly higher Gc and Mc CD11B and Gc

CD66b surface mean fluorescence intensity compared with the euglycemic patients with T2DM whose values were similar to those of the healthy controls. Further, they observed that CD16 expression in CD14+CD16+ Mc was elevated in all patients with T2DM, regardless of glycemic levels.

Caiado et al. [29] investigated a putative role for bone marrow-derived cells in the induction of epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition (EMT) as a marker for onset of **colorectal cancer metastasis**. In ectopic and orthotopic mouse models of colorectal cancer, they observed that bone marrow-derived CD11b(Itgam)⁺Jagged2 (Jag2)⁺ cells infiltrated primary tumors and surrounded tumor cells that exhibited diminished expression of E-cadherin and increased expression of vimentin, 2 hallmarks of EMT. Their in vitro coculture experiments showed that the bone marrow-derived CD11B⁺Jag2⁺ cells induced EMT through a Notch-dependent pathway. These might act as an indicator of colorectal cancer progression to metastatic levels of the disease.

Thyroid cancer (TC) is the most recurrent endocrine malignant tumor and is responsible for 70% of deaths due to endocrine cancers. Galdiero et al. [30] studied the involvement of tumor-associated neutrophils in TC. They observed that TC-derived soluble factors promoted neutrophil chemotaxis and survival. In addition, they found that each TC-CM induced morphological changes and activation of neutrophils (e.g., CD11B and CD66b upregulation and CD62L shedding) and modified neutrophils' kinetic properties.

There are a number of clinically effective treatments for stress-associated psychiatric diseases, including **major depressive disorder** (MDD). Accumulating evidence implicates altered glutamate signaling in MDD pathophysiology, suggesting that modulation of glutamate signaling cascades may offer novel therapeutic potential. Zhu et al. [31] reported that JHU-083, their recently developed prodrug of the glutaminase inhibitor 6-diazo-5-oxo-L-norleucine (DON) improves social avoidance and anhedonia-like behaviors in mice subjected to chronic social defeat stress (CSDS). They observed that JHU-083 normalized CSDS-induced increases in glutaminase activity specifically in microglia-enriched CD11B⁺ cells isolated from the prefrontal cortex and hippocampus. Further, they found that JHU-083 treatment reversed the CSDS-induced inflammatory activation of CD11B⁺ cells. Their results supported the importance of altered glutamate signaling in the behavioral abnormalities observed in the CSDS model, and identified glutaminase in microglia-enriched CD11B⁺ cells as a pharmacotherapeutic target implicated in the pathophysiology of stress-associated psychiatric conditions such as MDD.

Treatment failure in oral cancer is mainly caused by uncontrolled **cervical lymph node** (LN) metastasis. After reporting that CD11B⁺ cells were recruited into tumor hypoxic areas following radiation, leading to re-vascularization and relapse, Sugiura et al. [32] examined whether surgery induces hypoxia and stimulates lymphangiogenesis. They found that surgery on OSC-19 tumor induced LN metastases and hypoxia, followed by CD11B⁺ cell influx. Further, stimulation of lymphangiogenesis was observed in the CD11B⁺ cell influx area, as the tumor grew and the localization of CD11B⁺ cells was changed from the lymph nodules to the medullary sinuses. In conclusion, their experiments supported that fact that Surgery-induced hypoxia in oral tumors led to CD11B⁺ cell infiltration, lymphangiogenesis, and LN metastasis.

Role of macrophages in cholestatic liver fibrosis have remained unclear, though

they play important roles in the pathogenesis of chronic liver diseases. After reporting that long noncoding RNA-H19 (lncRNA-H19) contributed to cholangiocyte proliferation and cholestatic liver fibrosis of **biliary atresia (BA)**, Tian et al. [33] showed that monocyte/macrophage CD11B mRNA levels were increased significantly in livers of BA patients and positively correlated with the progression of liver inflammation and fibrosis.

Lupus nephritis (LN) develops in more than a third of all systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) patients and is the strongest predictor of morbidity and mortality. Villanueva et al. [34] reviewed the literature on the role of CD11B on leukocytes in LN. They included conclusions from several recent studies that showed that these ITGAM SNPs resulted in a CD11B protein that was less able to suppress TLR-dependent pro-inflammatory pathways in leukocytes, that activation of CD11B suppresses TLR-dependent pathways, including reductions in circulating levels of IFN I and anti-dsDNA antibodies, and that CD11B activation reduces LN in model systems. They observed that recent data strongly suggested that integrin CD11B was an exciting new therapeutic target in SLE and LN and that allosteric activation of CD11B was a novel therapeutic paradigm for effectively treating such autoimmune diseases.

Vaccination by inactivated vaccine is an effective strategy to prevent the COVID-19 pandemic. Cao et al. [35] delineated the landscape of the pre- and post-vaccination single-cell transcriptome, TCR (T cell antigen receptor) and BCR (B cell antigen receptor) expression profile of vaccinated candidates. Their cell-cell interaction analysis revealed that monocytes and dendritic cells could interact with these cells and initiate phagocytosis via ICAM1-ITGAM and ITGB2 signaling. Their study deciphered the detailed immunological response during **SARS-CoV-2** vaccination and infection.

Knee osteoarthritis (OA), is one of the most common degenerative joint diseases. 4 human neutrophil antigen (HNA) systems can be determined using each HNA allele by SNPs. Intharanut et al. [36] investigated the association of HNA SNPs and knee OA in the Thailand population. For this, in a case-control study, they performed the detection of HNA-1/3/4/5 alleles by PCR with sequence-specific priming (PCR-SSP) in participants with and without symptomatic knee OA. Among 200 participants, 117 (58.5%) had knee OA; 83 (41.5%) did not and were included as controls in this study. Further, An integrin subunit alpha M (ITGAM) nonsynonymous SNP, rs1143679, was markedly associated with symptomatic knee OA.

Since high expression of nuclear factor interleukin-3 (NFIL3) and ITGAM were found in serum samples from **Kawasaki disease (KD)** patients through bioinformatics analysis, Chen et al. [37] explored the biological functions of NFIL3 and ITGAM in KD serum-stimulated human coronary artery endothelial cells (HCAECs). They found that NFIL3 and ITGAM were up-regulated in serum from KD patients and KD serum-stimulated HCAECs. They also observed that down-regulation of NFIL3 or ITGAM inhibited KD serum-induced cell apoptosis and inflammatory response of HCAECs and promoted cell viability. Mechanistically, they found that NFIL3 promoted ITGAM transcription level and up-regulation of ITGAM reversed the improvement of NFIL3 down-regulation on KD serum-induced HCAEC injury. Thus, in conclusion NFIL3 aggravated KD serum-induced HCAEC injury by promoting ITGAM transcription.

Hyperuricemia is an essential risk factor in **chronic kidney disease (CKD)**. Liu et al. [38] investigated whether and how macrophage (ITGAM) contributed to hyperuricemia-

related CKD. They found that hyperuricemia-related CKD was characterized with elevated serum uric acid levels, activation of macrophage alternative (M2) polarization, impaired renal function, and kidney fibrosis. Notably, they confirmed the upregulated expression of macrophage ITGAM, activated pathway, and macrophage M2 polarization in injured kidneys. Their results indicated targeting macrophage ITGAM might be a promising therapeutic approach for preventing CKD. Bahabayi et al. [39] elucidated the significance of VNN2 expression in peripheral blood monocytes and its clinical relevance in primary **Sjögren's syndrome** (pSS). They observed high VNN2 expression in monocytes, with significantly higher levels in CD14⁺⁺ monocytes compared to ncMo. VNN2⁺ monocytes exhibited decreased expression of HLA and CD62L and increased expression of ITGAM, among other genetic factors, compared to VNN2⁻ monocytes. They concluded that detection of VNN2 expression in monocytes can aid in the auxiliary diagnosis of pSS.

Many of the different synergies represented as combinations of genes/proteins have been experimentally tested and published. However, there are combinations that have yet to be explored. I address the problem of identifying these unexplored combinations via use of a machine learning based search engine in the next section.

1.4. Insight behind the work

Across all search engines has the fundamental principle remains the same i.e to capture the pattern available in the data and based on that pattern, rank a list of queries. Different algorithms can be applied, however if the fundamental pattern is captured accurately, then the rankings will remain approximately the same, with slight variations, across the different kinds of search engines used. I use one search engine, however, vary the way the patterns are captured via use of different sensitivity methods. Each sensitivity method uses a different flavour/mathematical formulation to compute the sensitivity indices to estimate the influence of the involved factors. These involved factors are genes that play a role in cell biology, in the above research. The insight is that all methods will capture the sensitivity of the involved factors based on their recorded regulations and the search engine will rank the combination of factors based on these sensitivity indices. Since the role of involved factors are captured properly, the search engine will give appropriate rankings to the combinations, thus capturing which gene combinations might be playing significantly in a biological phenomena. The above work shows rankings for experimentally confirmed combinations as well as unexplored/untested combinations. These rankings are not just numbers. They point to the existence of biological synergy in the form of gene combinations, whether tested in wet lab or unexplored till now. Finally, the findings suggest that the rankings are conserved across the different sensitivity methods used.

1.5. Combinatorial search problem and a possible solution

In a recently published work Sinha [2], a frame work of a search engine was developed which can rank combinations of factors (genes/proteins) in a signaling pathway. The work uses SVM package by Joachims [40] in https://www.cs.cornell.edu/people/tj/svm_light/svm_rank.html. I use the adaptation to rank 2nd order gene

combinations. The sensitivity package by Pujol et al. [41] was used to develop the search engine pipeline. The current research uses the Hilbert Schmidt Independence Criterion (HSIC) and SOBOL method, implemented in the sensitivity package mentioned above. I use three different kernels under the HSIC method namely, • laplace, • linear and • rbf. For SOBOL method, I use • sobol-2002, and • sobol-jansen. Each of these variants or kernels have been implemented in the sensitivity package and option has been provided in the search engine code to generate the rankings for a particular gene, using a choice of a kernel/variant at a time. Technical details about the variants and kernels can be found in references cited in Pujol et al. [41].

2. Methods

2.1. Static data from Patel et al. [1]

Patel et al. [1] analyzed 160 meningioma samples from 140 patients, and according to the WHO histopathological classification system for meningioma, they found 121 tumors were of grade I (benign), 32 were of grade II (atypical), and 7 were of grade III (malignant). To determine whether meningiomas could be differentiated based on gene expression profiles, they used principal component analysis (PCA) on a discovery set of 97 tumors (i.e 77 WHO grade I and 20 WHO grade II). Next, they employed nonnegative matrix factorization (NMF) clustering (a unsupervised machine-learning approach) for $k = 2$ to $k = 7$ using the 1,500 genes that varied most among the tumor samples. They report that after 1,000 iterations, 3 clusters ($k = 3$) emerged as providing the best fit as determined by the consensus membership, cophenetic, and silhouette scores. They evaluated the cluster significance of the 3 subtypes using SigClust (Huang et al. [42]) and observed statistical significance between cluster boundaries, which exhibited significant differences in WHO grade representation.

2.2. Design for static data from Patel et al. [1]

The procedure begins with the listing of all C_k^n combinations for k number of genes from a total of n genes. Here n can be the choice of the biologist. k is ≥ 2 and $\leq (n - 1)$. Each of the combination of order k represent a unique set of interaction between the involved genetic factors. Since the sensitivity analysis methods require a sample for a particular observation, a steep gaussian distribution was generated with a jitter (noise) added to the deviation from the reported point measurement of 0.005. In this experiment, the distribution contained 10 measurements (including the point of measurement under consideration). This is repeated for each point of measurement.

To have an averaged ranking, the experiment was designed to run for 25 iterations. In each iteration, the datasets are combined in a specified format which go as input as per the requirement of a particular sensitivity analysis method. Thus for each p^{th} combination in C_k^n combinations, the dataset is prepared in a required format. Details of formatting the data have not been presented in the article to maintain the fluidity and brevity. Interested readers can find examples of forming the data in the sensitivity analysis package in R. Sensitivity analysis and its relevance in systems biology have

been covered in a recently published article by Sinha [43], which forms the foundation for this work. After the data has been transformed, vectorized programming is employed for density based sensitivity analysis and looping is employed for variance based sensitivity analysis to compute the required sensitivity indices for each of the p combinations.

After the above sensitivity indices have been stored for each of the p^{th} combination, for a chosen sensitivity analysis method, the next step in the design of experiment is conducted. Here, the indices are averaged per combination to have a mean index value. These index values form the discriminative features for a particular combination. For a k^{th} order combination, a vector of k elements or indices forms a feature vector. Thus for C_k^n combinations there will be C_k^n vectors, each containing k elements. Next, SVM_{learn}^{Rank} Joachims [40] is used to generate a model on default value C value of 20. In the current experiment on toy model C value has not been tuned. The training set helps in the generation of the model as the different gene combinations are numbered in order which are used as rank indices. The model is then used to generate score on the observations in the testing set using the $SVM_{classify}^{Rank}$ Joachims [40]. This is followed by sorting of these scores along with the rank indices already assigned to the gene combinations. The end result is a sorted order of the gene combinations based on the ranking score learned by the SVM^{Rank} algorithm.

Note that the following is the order in which the files should be executed in R Team [44], in order, for obtaining the desired results (Note that the code will not be explained here) - • use source("extractMeningiomadata.R") • use source("manuscript-2-2.R") • use source("SVMRank-Results-S-mean.R").

2.3. Translating the pipeline into code of execution in R

The execution begins by some preprocessing of the file containing the information regarding the down regulated genes via `source("extractMeningiomadata.R")`. The library containing the sensitivity analysis methods is then loaded in the interface using the command `library(sensitivity)` (Note - this package can be downloaded for free from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sensitivity/index.html>). Next a gaussian distribution for a particular transcript level for a gene is generated to have a sample. This is needed in the computation of sensitivity index for that particular gene. A gene of particular choice is selected (in blue) and the choice of the combination is made (here $k = 2$). Later a kernel is used (here rbf for HSIC method). 25 different indices are generated which help in generating aggregate rank using these 25 indices. The Support vector ranking algorithm is employed to generate the scores for different combinations and these scores are then sorted out. This is done using the command `source("SVMRank - Results - S - mean.R")`. A file is generated that contains the combinations in increasing order of influence. Note that 1 means lowest rank and vice versa, for 2^{nd} order combinations for any gene using a particular density based sensitivity index.

2.4. Regarding biological insight

For the recorded gene expression values, the sensitivity indices are computed. The search engine uses the kernel based density method. The kernel method takes the data, that is in a lower dimensional plane and projects it to a higher dimensional plane, with an idea that in a higher dimensional place, there exists a dot product between the projected data. To simply state, the idea is that in a higher dimensional plane the nonlinearities between the data (in lower dimensional plane) will be captured and the data may be segregated from each other via a hyperplane. So, irrespective of the method used to measure the gene expression values, if the measurements capture biological information (to whatever extent they can), then the kernel method will be able to capture the nonlinearities/synergies, if existing and allow the sensitivity analysis method (here density based method) to estimate the strength of influence of each of the factors. Based on the sensitivity indices of combinations of a particular order, the search engine ranks the combinations. Details of search engine are provided in the published work in Sinha [2].

It is important to note that the search engine will not give insight about the mechanism of synergy between the components of a combination. However, if the synergy exists between components of an unexplored/untested combination, then the sensitivity indices will capture the influence of these components taken together (which form a combination of interest) and will rank the combination appropriately. These rankings provide insight about which combination a biologist/oncologist might want to test in a forest of combinations for a given scenario in a cell (whether normal or pathological).

3. Results & Discussion

3.1. ITGAM related synergies

Note - ITGAM was found to be upregulated in Type B. Upregulation was defined as Type logFC to be > 1 and $FDR \leq 0.001$, in Patel et al. [1]. Also, sorting of scores by the machine learning algorithm were done in ascending order, i.e - top is lowest in ranking. A total of 392 2nd order combinations of ITGAM were recorded.

3.1.1. ITGAM - individual genes

The following genes in combination with ITGAM showed high rankings - CD4 molecule (CD4), CD74 molecule (CD74), collagen type XI alpha 1 chain (COL11A1), tetraspanin 32 (TSPAN32), solute carrier family 23 member 2 (SLC23A2), proprotein convertase subtilisin/kexin type 5 (PCSK5), nuclear factor of activated T cells 4 (NFATC4), matrix remodeling associated 5 (MXRA5), platelet derived growth factor receptor like (PDGFRL), epoxide hydrolase 3 (EPHX3), MINDY lysine 48 deubiquitinase 4 (MINDY4), procollagen C-endopeptidase enhancer (PCOLCE), endoglin (ENG), unc-5 netrin receptor B (UNC5B), cadherin related 23 (CDH23), cholinergic receptor nicotinic epsilon subunit (CHRNE), contactin associated protein 1 (CNTNAP1), peripheral myelin protein 22 (PMP22), tripartite motif containing 2 (TRIM2), SAM and SH3 domain containing 1 (SASH1), growth hormone receptor (GHR), Wnt ligand

secretion mediator (WLS), olfactomedin like 3 (OLFML3), immunoglobulin superfamily member 21 (IGSF21), neuropilin 2 (NRP2), chromosome 1 open reading frame 198 (C1orf198), plexin domain containing 2 (PLXDC2), PDZ and LIM domain 2 (PDLIM2), cysteine rich secretory protein LCCL domain containing 1 (CRISPLD1), C-C motif chemokine receptor 2 (CCR2), PHD finger protein 24 (PHF24), plasminogen activator, urokinase (PLAU), snail family transcriptional repressor 1 (SNAIL), hematopoietic cell signal transducer (HCST), leukocyte immunoglobulin like receptor B2 (LILRB2), myosin heavy chain 10 (MYH10), leucine rich repeats and calponin homology domain containing 1 (LRCH1), lymphocyte cytosolic protein 1 (LCP1), alpha kinase 3 (ALPK3), phospholipase C beta 2 (PLCB2), elastin microfibril interfacer 1 (EMILIN1), fibulin 5 (FBLN5), insulin like growth factor binding protein 4 (IGFBP4), RNA binding motif single stranded interacting protein 3 (RBMS3), family with sequence similarity 198, member A (FAM198A), CTD small phosphatase like (CTDSPL), aldehyde dehydrogenase 1 family member L1 (ALDH1L1), carbohydrate sulfotransferase 7 (CHST7), AT-rich interaction domain 5B (ARID5B), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 4 (KCNE4), dimethylarginine dimethylaminohydrolase 1 (DDAH1), myosin IE (MYO1E), SLAM family member 8 (SLAMF8), meiosis 1 associated protein (M1AP), trichohyalin (TCHH), coiled-coil-helix-coiled-coil-helix domain containing 6 (CHCHD6), sialic acid binding Ig like lectin 11 (SIGLEC11), NLR family pyrin domain containing 3 (NLRP3), coiled-coil domain containing 74A (CCDC74A), transmembrane protein 200A (TMEM200A), transmembrane protein 71 (TMEM71), sushi, von Willebrand factor type A, EGF and pentraxin domain containing 1 (SVEP1), trans-golgi network vesicle protein 23 homolog A (TVP23A), lactate dehydrogenase D (LDHD), filamin A interacting protein 1 like (FILIP1L), RAB31, member RAS oncogene family (RAB31), nephronectin (NPNT), atonal bHLH transcription factor 8 (ATOH8), G protein-coupled receptor 183 (GPR183), G protein-coupled receptor 27 (GPR27), microtubule associated protein 6 (MAP6), secretogranin II (SCG2), mono-ADP ribosylhydrolase 2 (MACROD2), StAR related lipid transfer domain containing 5 (STARD5), pseudopodium enriched atypical kinase 1 (PEAK1), sushi domain containing 5 (SUSD5), heart development protein with EGF like domains 1 (HEG1), homeobox B2 (HOXB2), CD248 molecule (CD248), purinergic receptor P2Y14 (P2RY14), family with sequence similarity 131 member A (FAM131A), calcium binding protein 4 (CABP4), solute carrier organic anion transporter family member 3A1 (SLCO3A1), BCL2 family apoptosis regulator BOK (BOK), MEF2 activating motif and SAP domain containing transcriptional regulator (MAMSTR), frizzled class receptor 8 (FZD8), myozenin 1 (MYOZ1), cysteine and serine rich nuclear protein 3 (CSRNP3), class II major histocompatibility complex transactivator (CIITA), serine rich and transmembrane domain containing 1 (SERTM1), potassium voltage-gated channel subfamily E regulatory subunit 1 (KCNE1), NME/NM23 family member 9 (NME9), biglycan (BGN), phospholipase C beta 1 (PLCB1), neurotrimin (NTM), regulator of G protein signaling 6 (RGS6), pappalysin 1 (PAPPA), nebulin (NEB), family with sequence similarity 43 member B (FAM43B), transmembrane protein 119 (TMEM119), olfactomedin like 1 (OLFML1), adrenoceptor alpha 2C (ADRA2C), protein kinase D1 (PRKD1), SHC adaptor protein 4 (SHC4), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily Z member 1 (CYP4Z1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily X member 1 (CYP4X1), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family

member A5, pseudogene (ANKRD20A5P), kelch repeat and BTB domain containing 12 (KBTBD12), low density lipoprotein receptor class A domain containing 2 (LDLRAD2), ectonucleoside triphosphate diphosphohydrolase 8 (ENTPD8), placenta associated 9 (PLAC9), nuclear GTPase, germinal center associated (NUGGC), family with sequence similarity 180 member A (FAM180A), serine/threonine kinase 31 (STK31), membrane metalloendopeptidase (MME), family with sequence similarity 180 member B (FAM180B), dishevelled binding antagonist of beta catenin 3 (DACT3), adenosine deaminase RNA specific B1 (ADARB1), chromosome 2 open reading frame 27A (C2orf27A), C-type lectin domain containing 9A (CLEC9A), DLG associated protein 2 (DLGAP2), metallothionein 1F (MT1F), matrix metalloproteinase 17 (MMP17), delta like canonical Notch ligand 1 (DLL1), zinc finger protein 521 (ZNF521), ryanodine receptor 3 (RYR3), dual specificity phosphatase and pro isomerase domain containing 1 (DUSP27 / DUSP29), RNA, U6 small nuclear 529, pseudogene (RNU6-529P), ras homolog family member T1 pseudogene 2 (RHOT1P2), phospholipid phosphatase 4 (PLPP4), synaptotagmin 15 (SYT15), family with sequence similarity 155 member A (FAM155A), transmembrane protein 240 (TMEM240), vitrin (VIT), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A9, pseudogene (ANKRD20A9P), glutathione peroxidase 3 (GPX3), high mobility group box 3 pseudogene 7 (HMGB3P7), ankyrin repeat domain 20 family member A11, pseudogene (ANKRD20A11P), teneurin transmembrane protein 3 (TENM3), long intergenic non-protein coding RNA 937 (LINC00937), ITGB2 antisense RNA 1 (ITGB2-AS1), cytochrome P450 family 4 subfamily F member 29, pseudogene (CYP4F29P) and sorting nexin 18 pseudogene 13 (SNX18P13).

Using the adaptation of the above mentioned search engine, I tabulate the rankings of 2nd order combination of ITGAM with the above list, that were reported to be upregulated in Patel et al. [1]. Table 1 and 2 shows rankings of these combinations. Followed by this is the unexplored combinatorial hypotheses in table 3 generated from analysis of the ranks in table 1 and 2.

One can also interpret the results of the table 1 and 2 graphically, with the following influences - • Individual members w.r.t ITGAM with ITGAM – > CD4 CD74 COL11A1 TSPAN32 SLC23A2 PCSK5 NFATC4 MXRA5 PDGFRL EPHX3 MINDY4 PCOLCE ENG UNC5B CDH23 CHRNE CNTNAP1 PMP22 TRIM2 SASH1 GHR WLS OLFML3 IGSF21 NRP2 C1orf198 PLXDC2 PDLIM2 CRISPLD1 CCR2 PHF24 PLAUI SNAI1 HCST LILRB2 MYH10 LRCH1 LCP1 ALPK3 PLCB2 EMILIN1 FBLN5 IGFBP4 RBMS3 FAM198A CTD-SPL ALDH1L1 CHST7 ARID5B KCNE4 DDAH1 MYO1E SLAMF8 M1AP TCHH CHCHD6 SIGLEC11 NLRP3 CCDC74A TMEM200A TMEM71 SVEP1 TVP23A LDHD FILIP1L RAB31 NPNT ATOH8 GPR183 GPR27 MAP6 SCG2 MACROD2 STARD5 PEAK1 SUSD5 HEG1 HOXB2 CD248 P2RY14 FAM131A CABP4 SLCO3A1 BOK MAMSTR FZD8 MYOZ1 CSRNP3 CIITA SERTM1 KCNE1 NME9 BGN PLCB1 NTM RGS6 PAPP A NEB FAM43B TMEM119 OLFML1 ADRA2C PRKD1 SHC4 CYP4Z1 CYP4X1 ANKRD20A5P KBTBD12 LDLRAD2 ENTPD8 PLAC9 NUGGC FAM180A STK31 MME FAM180B DACT3 ADARB1 C2orf27A CLEC9A DLGAP2 MT1F MMP17 DLL1 ZNF521 RYR3 DUSP27 RNU6-529P RHOT1P2 PLPP4 SYT15 FAM155A TMEM240 VIT ANKRD20A9P GPX3 HMGB3P7 ANKRD20A11P TENM3 LINC00937 ITGB2-AS1 CYP4F29P SNX18P13.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ITGAM									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ITGAM									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
CD4 - ITGAM	371	355	249	325	CD74 - ITGAM	182	356	224	367
COL11A1 - ITGAM	305	336	234	338	TSPAN32 - ITGAM	322	219	248	61
SLC23A2 - ITGAM	194	351	259	332	PCSK5 - ITGAM	378	258	292	59
NFATC4 - ITGAM	326	378	271	360	MXRA5 - ITGAM	260	164	240	293
PDGFRL - ITGAM	239	199	230	376	EPHX3 - ITGAM	271	268	56	208
MINDY4 - ITGAM	291	80	214	282	PCOLCE - ITGAM	198	256	235	289
ENG - ITGAM	250	134	268	365	UNC5B - ITGAM	241	254	136	337
CDH23 - ITGAM	251	291	125	230	CHRNE - ITGAM	129	304	279	320
CNTNAP1 - ITGAM	246	374	253	343	PMP22 - ITGAM	388	330	282	354
TRIM2 - ITGAM	168	357	297	346	SASH1 - ITGAM	273	279	204	9
GHR - ITGAM	313	229	232	366	WLS - ITGAM	279	335	231	274
OLFML3 - ITGAM	265	299	177	250	IGSF21 - ITGAM	212	303	131	305
NRP2 - ITGAM	123	388	250	273	C1orf198 - ITGAM	298	381	254	355
PLXDC2 - ITGAM	336	216	138	301	PDLIM2 - ITGAM	315	226	186	318
CRISPLD1 - ITGAM	283	240	202	86	CCR2 - ITGAM	252	344	287	4
PHF24 - ITGAM	231	339	272	390	PLAU - ITGAM	93	323	245	383
SNAI1 - ITGAM	230	274	158	336	HCST - ITGAM	361	369	244	339
LILRB2 - ITGAM	238	300	238	311	MYH10 - ITGAM	299	292	160	333
LRCH1 - ITGAM	261	271	251	350	LCP1 - ITGAM	208	322	275	345
ALPK3 - ITGAM	308	332	291	99	PLCB2 - ITGAM	256	360	262	378
EMILIN1 - ITGAM	337	314	296	44	FBLN5 - ITGAM	295	352	227	344
IGFBP4 - ITGAM	277	387	239	349	RBMS3 - ITGAM	306	238	205	76
FAM198A - ITGAM	235	337	278	19	CTDSPL - ITGAM	338	253	207	328
ALDH1L1 - ITGAM	126	288	247	340	CHST7 - ITGAM	195	267	273	370
ARID5B - ITGAM	309	333	246	319	KCNE4 - ITGAM	154	280	233	385
DDAH1 - ITGAM	323	313	228	51	MYO1E - ITGAM	236	331	266	304
SLAMF8 - ITGAM	213	348	255	357	M1AP - ITGAM	332	372	225	322
TCHH - ITGAM	217	227	236	123	CHCHD6 - ITGAM	224	234	286	36
SIGLEC11 - ITGAM	263	260	148	316	NLRP3 - ITGAM	207	277	242	330
CCDC74A - ITGAM	293	272	220	321	TMEM200A - ITGAM	320	186	203	381
TMEM71 - ITGAM	339	282	211	331	SVEP1 - ITGAM	216	200	31	241
TVP23A - ITGAM	244	307	24	369	LDHD - ITGAM	280	341	241	361
FILIP1L - ITGAM	209	212	127	314	RAB31 - ITGAM	310	349	180	387
NPNT - ITGAM	324	236	295	29	ATOH8 - ITGAM	92	248	264	312
GPR183 - ITGAM	357	228	265	308	GPR27 - ITGAM	255	237	342	266
MAP6 - ITGAM	381	185	325	351	SCG2 - ITGAM	383	380	378	177

Table 1: 2nd order interaction ranking between ITGAM VS Individual members.

4. Conclusion

Presented here are a range of multiple synergistic ITGAM 2nd order combinations that were ranked via a machine learning based search engine. Via majority voting across the ranking methods it was possible to find plausible unexplored synergistic combinations of ITGAM-X that might be prevalent in meningioma.

Conflict of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

RANKING INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS VS ITGAM									
RANKING OF INDIVIDUAL MEMBERS W.R.T ITGAM									
	laplace	linear	rbf	jansen		laplace	linear	rbf	jansen
MACROD2 - ITGAM	201	324	353	5	STARD5 - ITGAM	352	290	305	68
PEAK1 - ITGAM	161	266	311	368	SUSD5 - ITGAM	301	342	318	287
HEG1 - ITGAM	321	77	336	353	HOXB2 - ITGAM	316	204	370	94
CD248 - ITGAM	156	346	334	327	P2RY14 - ITGAM	348	179	371	245
FAM131A - ITGAM	187	210	319	392	CABP4 - ITGAM	352	205	355	83
SLCO3A1 - ITGAM	233	365	351	225	BOK - ITGAM	248	201	359	296
MAMSTR - ITGAM	276	264	299	335	FZD8 - ITGAM	211	325	331	363
MYOZ1 - ITGAM	360	245	330	167	CSRN3 - ITGAM	375	116	276	373
CIITA - ITGAM	190	225	302	389	SERTM1 - ITGAM	379	350	362	215
KCNE1 - ITGAM	314	329	280	25	NME9 - ITGAM	229	305	354	79
BGN - ITGAM	345	375	316	46	PLCB1 - ITGAM	270	230	385	97
NTM - ITGAM	386	243	357	156	RGS6 - ITGAM	363	392	343	207
PAPPA - ITGAM	369	343	386	176	NEB - ITGAM	178	295	326	362
FAM43B - ITGAM	319	217	322	302	TMEM119 - ITGAM	356	327	380	133
OLFML1 - ITGAM	367	319	329	118	ADRA2C - ITGAM	365	263	314	253
PRKD1 - ITGAM	359	370	379	232	SHC4 - ITGAM	303	257	372	102
CYP4Z1 - ITGAM	290	302	321	388	CYP4X1 - ITGAM	258	92	288	277
ANKRD20A5P - ITGAM	382	354	375	214	KBTBD12 - ITGAM	214	285	308	146
LDLRAD2 - ITGAM	374	358	360	204	ENTPD8 - ITGAM	366	293	328	256
PLAC9 - ITGAM	380	361	391	112	NUGGC - ITGAM	370	320	390	310
FAM180A - ITGAM	385	376	387	145	STK31 - ITGAM	202	208	307	22
MME - ITGAM	389	390	374	197	FAM180B - ITGAM	384	379	392	165
DACT3 - ITGAM	340	287	270	391	ADARB1 - ITGAM	249	301	335	37
C2orf27A - ITGAM	311	110	289	313	CLEC9A - ITGAM	253	373	381	217
DLGAP2 - ITGAM	387	389	363	228	MT1F - ITGAM	292	345	306	315
MMP17 - ITGAM	327	270	377	119	DLL1 - ITGAM	358	353	324	257
ZNF521 - ITGAM	391	383	367	178	RYR3 - ITGAM	344	316	338	221
DUSP27 - ITGAM	346	84	310	342	RNU6-529P - ITGAM	204	139	320	347
RHOT1P2 - ITGAM	390	377	366	107	PLPP4 - ITGAM	377	384	352	201
SYT15 - ITGAM	254	215	344	356	FAM155A - ITGAM	349	252	339	251
TMEM240 - ITGAM	317	362	294	82	VIT - ITGAM	376	386	382	199
ANKRD20A9P - ITGAM	372	385	389	186	GPX3 - ITGAM	312	382	384	116
HMGB3P7 - ITGAM	294	276	332	238	ANKRD20A11P - ITGAM	350	308	388	212
TENM3 - ITGAM	373	340	373	188	LINC00937 - ITGAM	228	289	333	364
ITGB2-AS1 - ITGAM	329	326	365	244	CYP4F29P - ITGAM	392	312	356	203
SNX18P13 - ITGAM	364	371	364	134					

Table 2: 2nd order interaction ranking between ITGAM VS Individual members.

Author's contributions

Concept, design, in silico implementation - SS. Analysis and interpretation of results - SS. Manuscript writing - SS. Manuscript revision - SS. Approval of manuscript - SS

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Source of Data

Data used in this research work was released in a publication in Patel et al. [1]. Permission to use, granted by PNAS.

UNEXPLORED COMBINATORIAL HYPOTHESES

Individual members w.r.t ITGAM

CD4 / CD74 / COL11A1 / TSPAN32 / SLC23A2 ...
 / PCSK5 / NFATC4 / MXRA5 / PDGFRL / EPHX3 ...
 MINDY4 / PCOLCE / ENG / UNC5B / CDH23 ...
 CHRNE / CNTNAP1 / PMP22 / TRIM2 / SASH1 ...
 GHR / WLS / OLFML3 / IGSF21 / NRP2 / C1orf198 ...
 PLXDC2 / PDLIM2 / CRISPLD1 / CCR2 / PHF24 ...
 PLAU / SNAI1 / HCST / LILRB2 / MYH10 / LRCH1 ...
 LCP1 / ALPK3 / PLCB2 / EMILIN1 / FBLN5 / IGFBP4 ...
 RBMS3 / FAM198A / CTDSPL / ALDH1L1 / CHST7 ...
 ARID5B / KCNE4 / DDAH1 / MYO1E / SLAMF8 / M1AP ...
 TCHH / CHCHD6 / SIGLEC11 / NLRP3 / CCDC74A ...
 TMEM200A / TMEM71 / SVEP1 / TVP23A / LDHD ...
 FILIP1L / RAB31 / NPNT / ATOH8 / GPR183 / GPR27 ...
 MAP6 / SCG2 / MACROD2 / STARD5 / PEAK1 / SUSD5 ...
 HEG1 / HOXB2 / CD248 / P2RY14 / FAM131A / CABP4 ...
 SLCO3A1 / BOK / MAMSTR / FZD8 / MYOZ1 / CSRNP3 ...
 CIITA / SERTM1 / KCNE1 / NME9 / BGN / PLCB1 / NTM ...
 RGS6 / PAPP / NEB / FAM43B / TMEM119 / OLFML1 ...
 ADRA2C / PRKD1 / SHC4 / CYP4Z1 / CYP4X1 / ANKRD20A5P ...
 KBTBD12 / LDLRAD2 / ENTPD8 / PLAC9 / NUGGC / FAM180A ...
 STK31 / MME / FAM180B / DACT3 / ADARB1 / C2orf27A ...
 CLEC9A / DLGAP2 / MT1F / MMP17 / DLL1 / ZNF521 ...
 RYR3 / DUSP27 / RNU6-529P / RHOT1P2 / PLPP4 ...
 SYT15 / FAM155A / TMEM240 / VIT / ANKRD20A9P ...
 GPX3 / HMGB3P7 / ANKRD20A11P / TENM3 / LINC00937 ...
 ITGB2-AS1 / CYP4F29P / SNX18P13 ITGAM

Table 3: 2nd order combinatorial hypotheses between ITGAM and Individual members.

References

- [1] A. J. Patel, Y.-W. Wan, R. Al-Ouran, J.-P. Revelli, M. F. Cardenas, M. Oneissi, L. Xi, A. Jalali, J. F. Magnotti, D. M. Muzny, et al., Molecular profiling predicts meningioma recurrence and reveals loss of dream complex repression in aggressive tumors, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 116 (2019) 21715–21726.
- [2] S. Sinha, Machine learning ranking of plausible (un) explored synergistic gene combinations using sensitivity indices of time series measurements of wnt signaling pathway, *Integrative Biology* 16 (2024) zya020.
- [3] D. N. Louis, A. Perry, P. Wesseling, D. J. Brat, I. A. Cree, D. Figarella-Branger, C. Hawkins, H. Ng, S. M. Pfister, G. Reifenberger, et al., The 2021 who classifi-

- cation of tumors of the central nervous system: a summary, *Neuro-oncology* 23 (2021) 1231–1251.
- [4] S. H. Torp, O. Solheim, A. J. Skjulsvik, The who 2021 classification of central nervous system tumours: a practical update on what neurosurgeons need to know a minireview, *Acta Neurochirurgica* 164 (2022) 2453–2464.
- [5] A. Czarnetzki, E. Schwaderer, C. M. Pusch, Fossil record of meningioma, *The Lancet* 362 (2003) 408.
- [6] D. O. Okonkwo, E. R. Laws Jr, Meningiomas: historical perspective, in: *Meningiomas*, Springer, 2009, pp. 3–10.
- [7] S. Paterniti, Meningiomas surgery in Italy in the nineteenth century: Historical review, *Austin Neurosurg Open Access* 2 (2015) 1030.
- [8] Z. Pecchioli, Soria di un fungo della dura madre, operato collestirpazione dal professor zanobi pecchioli, *Nuovo Giornale de'LetteratiScienze* 36 (1838) 39–44.
- [9] H. Cushing, The meningiomas (dural endotheliomas): their source, and favoured seats of origin, *Brain* 45 (1922) 282–316.
- [10] W. contributors, Meningioma — Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia, 2024. URL: <https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Meningioma&oldid=1259055917>, online; accessed 11-April-2025.
- [11] M. N. Pamir, P. M. Black, R. Fahlbusch, *Meningiomas : a comprehensive text*, Elsevier Health Sciences, 2010.
- [12] F. Szulzewsky, H. N. Thirimanne, E. C. Holland, Meningioma: current updates on genetics, classification, and mouse modeling, *Upsala Journal of Medical Sciences* 129 (2024) 10–48101.
- [13] M. W. Pierce, E. Remold-O'Donnell, R. F. Todd III, M. A. Arnaout, N-terminal sequence of human leukocyte glycoprotein mol: conservation across species and homology to platelet iib/iiia, *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta (BBA)-Protein Structure and Molecular Enzymology* 874 (1986) 368–371.
- [14] M. A. Arnaout, E. Remold-O'Donnell, M. W. Pierce, P. Harris, D. G. Tenen, Molecular cloning of the alpha subunit of human and guinea pig leukocyte adhesion glycoprotein mol: chromosomal localization and homology to the alpha subunits of integrins., *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 85 (1988) 2776–2780.
- [15] A. Corbi, T. Kishimoto, L. Miller, T. Springer, The human leukocyte adhesion glycoprotein mac-1 (complement receptor type 3, cd11b) alpha subunit. cloning, primary structure, and relation to the integrins, von willebrand factor and factor b., *Journal of Biological Chemistry* 263 (1988) 12403–12411.

- [16] N. Komura, Y. Ikeda, N. Masuda, Y. Umezawa, K. Ito, M. Kizaki, K. Umezawa, Designed atra analogue active against atra-resistant acute promyelocytic leukemia cells having a single nucleotide substitution in their retinoic acid receptor, *Leukemia research* 31 (2007) 301–313.
- [17] P. Rhein, S. Scheid, R. Ratei, C. Hagemeyer, K. Seeger, R. Kirschner-Schwabe, A. Moericke, M. Schrappe, R. Spang, W. Ludwig, et al., Gene expression shift towards normal b cells, decreased proliferative capacity and distinct surface receptors characterize leukemic blasts persisting during induction therapy in childhood acute lymphoblastic leukemia, *Leukemia* 21 (2007) 897–905.
- [18] T. Yamagata, H. Sugiura, T. Yokoyama, S. Yanagisawa, T. Ichikawa, K. Ueshima, K. Akamatsu, T. Hirano, M. Nakanishi, Y. Yamagata, et al., Overexpression of cd-11b and cxcr1 on circulating neutrophils: its possible role in copd, *Chest* 132 (2007) 890–899.
- [19] G. Hom, R. R. Graham, B. Modrek, K. E. Taylor, W. Ortmann, S. Garnier, A. T. Lee, S. A. Chung, R. C. Ferreira, P. K. Pant, et al., Association of systemic lupus erythematosus with c8orf13–blk and itgam–itgax, *New England Journal of Medicine* 358 (2008) 900–909.
- [20] A. Seth, J. Cui, E. To, M. Kwee, J. Matsubara, Complement-associated deposits in the human retina, *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science* 49 (2008) 743–750.
- [21] R. Kallio, H. Aalto, A. Takala, P. Ohtonen, J. Collan, S. Siitonen, H. Joensuu, H. Syrjala, H. Repo, Expression of cd11b/cd18 adhesion molecules on circulating phagocytes a novel aid to diagnose infection in patients with cancer, *Supportive care in cancer* 16 (2008) 1389–1396.
- [22] M. Suzukawa, R. Koketsu, M. Iikura, S. Nakae, K. Matsumoto, H. Nagase, H. Saito, K. Matsushima, K. Ohta, K. Yamamoto, et al., Interleukin-33 enhances adhesion, cd11b expression and survival in human eosinophils, *Laboratory investigation* 88 (2008) 1245–1253.
- [23] M. Alfano, S. A. Mariani, C. Elia, R. Pardi, F. Blasi, G. Poli, Ligand-engaged urokinase-type plasminogen activator receptor and activation of the cd11b/cd18 integrin inhibit late events of hiv expression in monocytic cells, *Blood, The Journal of the American Society of Hematology* 113 (2009) 1699–1709.
- [24] E. R. Hernandez, B. Fuste, A. Cases, R. Tonda, G. Escolar, A. Ordinas, M. Diaz-Ricart, Haemodialysis through a cellulose membrane induces dephosphorylation of cd11b and promotes leukocyte adhesion to endothelial cells, *Clinical and Investigative Medicine* 32 (2009) E48–E56.
- [25] K. C. McKenna, K. M. Beatty, R. A. Bilonick, L. Schoenfield, K. L. Lathrop, A. D. Singh, Activated cd11b+ cd15+ granulocytes increase in the blood of patients with uveal melanoma, *Investigative ophthalmology & visual science* 50 (2009) 4295–4303.

- [26] A. A. Sabri, R. Reda, A. A. Ali, A. A. Alim, S. I. Bakr, R. A. Abo-Shady, H. G. Mohamed, R. Saleh, Effect of surgically-induced weight loss on inflammatory mediators and peripheral blood monocyte cd11b expression in morbid obesity, *Egyptian Journal of Immunology* 17 (2010) 19–28.
- [27] I. M. Rea, S. E. McNerlan, D. H. Alexander, M. E. Armstrong, Blood pressure and $\text{tnf-}\alpha$ act synergistically to increase leucocyte cd11b adhesion molecule expression in the belfast study: implications for better blood pressure control in ageing, *Age* 35 (2013) 197–205.
- [28] P. Horvath, S. R. Oliver, G. Ganesan, F. P. Zaldivar Jr, S. Radom-Aizik, P. R. Galassetti, Fasting glucose level modulates cell surface expression of cd11b and cd66b in granulocytes and monocytes of patients with type 2 diabetes, *Journal of investigative medicine* 61 (2013) 972–977.
- [29] F. Caiado, T. Carvalho, I. Rosa, L. Remédio, A. Costa, J. Matos, B. Heissig, H. Yagita, K. Hattori, J. P. da Silva, et al., Bone marrow-derived cd11b+ jagged2+ cells promote epithelial-to-mesenchymal transition and metastasization in colorectal cancer, *Cancer research* 73 (2013) 4233–4246.
- [30] M. R. Galdiero, G. Varricchi, S. Loffredo, C. Bellevicine, T. Lansione, A. L. Ferrara, R. Iannone, S. di Somma, F. Borriello, E. Clery, et al., Potential involvement of neutrophils in human thyroid cancer, *PLoS One* 13 (2018) e0199740.
- [31] X. Zhu, M. T. Nedelcovych, A. G. Thomas, Y. Hasegawa, A. Moreno-Megui, W. Coomer, V. Vohra, A. Saito, G. Perez, Y. Wu, et al., Jhu-083 selectively blocks glutaminase activity in brain cd11b+ cells and prevents depression-associated behaviors induced by chronic social defeat stress, *Neuropsychopharmacology* 44 (2019) 683–694.
- [32] K. Sugiura, S. Nakajima, I. Kato, M. Okubo-Sato, Y. Nakazawa, K. Mitsudo, M. Kioi, Hypoxia and cd11b+ cell influx are strongly associated with lymph node metastasis of oral cancer, *Anticancer Research* 40 (2020) 6845–6852.
- [33] X. Tian, Y. Wang, Y. Lu, W. Wang, J. Du, S. Chen, H. Zhou, W. Cai, Y. Xiao, Conditional depletion of macrophages ameliorates cholestatic liver injury and fibrosis via lncrna-h19, *Cell death & disease* 12 (2021) 646.
- [34] V. Villanueva, X. Li, V. Jimenez, H. M. Faridi, V. Gupta, Cd11b agonists offer a novel approach for treating lupus nephritis, *Translational Research* 245 (2022) 41–54.
- [35] X. Cao, X. Chen, Y. Zhu, X. Gou, K. Yan, B. Yang, D. Men, L. Liu, Y.-a. Zhang, G. Cao, Single-cell transcriptome landscape and antigen receptor dynamic during sars-cov-2 vaccination, *Genes & Diseases* 10 (2023) 1675–1686.
- [36] K. Intharanut, P. Suttanon, O. Nathalang, Integrin subunit alpha m, itgam nonsynonymous snp is associated with knee osteoarthritis among thais: A case-control study, *Current Issues in Molecular Biology* 45 (2023) 4168–4180.

- [37] L. Chen, Z. Shangguan, Z. Dong, Q. Deng, Y. Ding, S. Yang, Nfil3 aggravates human coronary artery endothelial cell injury by promoting itgam transcription in kawasaki disease, *Hematology* 28 (2023) 2277502.
- [38] J. Liu, F. Guo, X. Chen, P. Fu, L. Ma, Integrin α m promotes macrophage alternative m2 polarization in hyperuricemia-related chronic kidney disease, *MedComm* 5 (2024) e580.
- [39] A. Bahabayi, X. Alimu, G. Wang, Y. Gao, Y. Chen, J. Zhao, X. Lian, Q. Li, Z. Xiong, Z. Zhang, et al., Vnn2-expressing circulating monocytes exhibit unique functional characteristics and are decreased in patients with primary sjögren’s syndrome, *Journal of Autoimmunity* 147 (2024) 103275.
- [40] T. Joachims, Training linear svms in linear time, in: *Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining*, ACM, 2006, pp. 217–226.
- [41] G. Pujol, B. Iooss, A. Janon, K. Boumhaout, S. Da Veiga, J. Fruth, L. Gilquin, J. Guillaume, L. Le Gratiot, P. Lemaitre, et al., Sensitivity: global sensitivity analysis of model outputs, *R package version 1* (2017).
- [42] H. Huang, Y. Liu, M. Yuan, J. Marron, Statistical significance of clustering using soft thresholding, *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics* 24 (2015) 975–993.
- [43] S. Sinha, Hilbert-schmidt and sobol sensitivity indices for static and time series wnt signaling measurements in colorectal cancer-part a, *BMC systems biology* 11 (2017) 120.
- [44] R. C. Team, *R language definition*, Vienna, Austria: R foundation for statistical computing 3 (2000) 116.